

SYNTHESSES OF N-MANNICH BASES OF ISO VALERAMIDE

TABLE 1—N-MANNICH BASES OF ISO VALERAMIDE

No.	-R	*m.p.(°C)	Yield %	Molecular formula	** Percentage of Nitrogen		‡ Equivalent Wt.	
					Found	Required	Found	Required
1.	Dibenzylaminomethyl	90—91	80	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O	9.08	9.03	310.5	310.0
2.	Dicyclohexylaminomethyl	319—20	80	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ N ₂ O	9.49	9.52	293.2	294.0
3.	Morpholinomethyl	199—200	80	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	13.82	14.00	200.5	200.0
4.	N,N'-bis Piperazinomethyl	204—205	70	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₂	17.90	17.94	309.6	312.0
5.	Dipropylaminomethyl	189—90	75	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O	13.02	13.08	213.8	214.0
6.	Di-n-butylaminomethyl	241—42	68	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O	11.03	11.10	244.2	242.0
7.	Pyrrolidinomethyl	176—77	80	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	15.20	15.21	183.4	184.0
8.	Dimethylaminomethyl	181—82	60	C ₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	17.60	17.72	158.4	158.0
9.	Diethylaminomethyl	162—63	53	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	14.96	15.05	185.1	186.0
10.	Piperidinomethyl	239—40	70	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O	14.55	14.64	199.0	198.0

* All m.ps. are uncorrected.

** Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method.

‡ Eq. Weight was found by visual nonaqueous titration.

which was previously dried to a constant weight. The precipitate was washed with cold water and alcohol, and finally dried to a constant weight in a vacuum desiccator over phosphorus pentoxide.

All the relevant data about the reported compounds are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The pharmacological work on these compounds is in progress and will be reported later on.

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF N-MANNICH BASES OF ISO VALERAMIDE AS THEIR REINECKATES

No.	-R	Weight of Mannich base taken on (g)	Wt. of Reineckate salt	
			found (g)	required (g)
1.	Dibenzylaminomethyl	0.1024	0.2081	0.2076
2.	Dicyclohexylaminomethyl	0.1006	0.2130	0.2124
3.	Morpholinomethyl	0.1044	0.2717	0.2706
4.	N,N'-bis-Piperazinomethyl	0.1036	0.2304	0.2292
5.	Dipropylaminomethyl	0.1024	0.2552	0.2548
6.	Di-n-butylaminomethyl	0.1048	0.2448	0.2436
7.	Pyrrolidinomethyl	0.1102	0.3022	0.3099
8.	Dimethylaminomethyl	0.1000	0.3024	0.3015
9.	Diethylaminomethyl	0.1028	0.2798	0.2781
10.	Piperidinomethyl	0.1034	0.2740	0.2722

This estimation may also serve as a method for the determination of equivalent weight of N-Mannich bases.

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